

Development and Evaluation of a Library Book Finding System with a Proximity Detector

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Abstract- The efficiency of locating books in large libraries is a significant challenge, often leading to user frustration and reduced satisfaction. This study addresses these issues by developing and evaluating a Library Book Finding System that integrates Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technologies to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of locating books. The system utilizes mobile applications and strategically placed sensors to significantly reduce search time and improve user experience. The research employed a descriptive and developmental approach, using the Rapid Application Development (RAD) model to facilitate quick software deployment. User satisfaction and system usability were quantitatively assessed using the Post- Study System Usability Questionnaire (PSSUQ) and qualitatively through text case analysis. Results indicated that 85% of users experienced increased efficiency in locating books, 88% trusted the accuracy of the information provided, and 83% appreciated the system's user-friendly interface. The study highlights the potential of RFID and BLE technologies to create intelligent library environments, with data analytics playing a crucial role in refining the system to meet user needs better and enhance overall library service delivery.

Keywords: Library Book Finding System, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) Technology, Proximity Detection, Smart Library.

I. INTRODUCTION

Libraries have long been the cornerstone of academic institutions, pivotal in supporting education, research, and knowledge dissemination. In the Fifth Industrial Revolution context, where integrating advanced technologies is crucial for improving traditional systems, libraries worldwide are increasingly adopting digital solutions to enhance their services [1]. Technologies such as Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) have been successfully implemented in many libraries globally, streamlining resource management, reducing manual errors, and significantly improving user satisfaction [2]. These innovations enable libraries to stay relevant in an era where digital information is easily accessible, ensuring that physical library resources remain organized and accessible while improving the overall efficiency of library operations.

However, in the ASEAN region, particularly in developing countries like the Philippines, the adoption of such advanced technologies in been

slower, although there is a growing momentum. For instance, state universities in the Philippines, such as Carlos Hilado Memorial State University (CHMSU), still largely depend on manual cataloging systems. While traditional, these systems have become increasingly inadequate to meet the demands of a growing student population and the expanding volume of library resources. Limited funding and technological infrastructure further restrict the ability of these institutions to implement comprehensive digital solutions. As a result, libraries in the region continue to struggle with persistent issues such as book

misplacement and inefficient manual search processes, significantly diminishing the user experience. Research shows that approximately 5.6% of library resources are misplaced, while 65% are on the correct shelves but not in their designated positions [3]. These challenges underscore the need for more efficient and effective library management systems to improve operational workflow and user satisfaction.

The successful implementation of RFID and BLE technologies in libraries worldwide has demonstrated the potential of these systems to address the aforementioned issues. For instance, Cebu Normal University in the Philippines developed a low-cost book-tracking mobile application, which has significantly improved the efficiency of library operations and boosted user satisfaction [4]. In India, Veermata Jijabai Technological Institute introduced an application with RFID integration, mapping features, and a resource tracker, streamlining resource management and optimizing library services [5]. Similarly, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University in Thailand implemented BLE transmitters and beacons to facilitate seamless indoor navigation, greatly enhancing the user experience within their library [6]. These examples demonstrate that RFID and BLE technologies can provide scalable, cost-effective solutions that modernize library systems, making them more efficient and user-friendly.

Despite these global advancements, integrating RFID and BLE technologies remains underexplored in many libraries in the Philippines, leaving a significant gap in modern library management systems. This study addresses this gap by developing and evaluating a Library Book Finding System with a Proximity Detector at CHMSU. Specifically, the study introduced a system that integrates RFID and BLE technologies to accurately and efficiently locate books within the library. The objectives include assessing the current state of the library's resource management, implementing the proposed system, and measuring its usability and functionality. By achieving these goals, the study seeks to contribute to modernizing library management practices in the Philippines. Ultimately, this research aims to improve operational efficiency and enhance the academic experience for library users, ensuring that libraries remain vital centers of learning in the digital age.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-developmental design to address library users' challenges in locating books while developing an advanced technological solution to enhance the accuracy and

efficiency of book-finding tasks. The descriptive component provided an understanding of the inefficiencies in existing library systems through surveys and observations of current processes. The developmental aspect focused on designing and refining a proximity detection system with RFID and BLE technologies. This approach ensured that the system addressed real-world library challenges and incorporated user needs, as informed by recent literature [7].

System Development Framework

The Rapid Application Development (RAD) framework guided the creation of the Library Book Finding System with Proximity Detection. Its emphasis on iterative prototyping and quick feedback loops was ideal for ensuring user needs were continually integrated throughout the system's development. This approach enabled rapid design, testing, and refinement cycles, allowing the system to evolve dynamically based on ongoing user input [8]. The system's development followed four phases, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure. 1. Rapid Application Development Framework.

Requirements Gathering and Planning. In this phase, system requirements were gathered through consultations with library staff, users, and technical experts. These consultations involved interviews, surveys, and focus groups to identify the challenges associated with book tracking and user interaction within the library. Special attention was given to user interface design and technical functionalities that could enhance accuracy, ease of use, and security. Table I presents the core functional requirements of the system.

TABLE I. FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENT

Functional Requirement	Description
User Search Interface	Allows users to search for books by title, author, ISBN, or keywords.
Proximity Detection	Utilizes proximity sensors to identify the location of books within the library.
Book Location Display	Shows the exact location of the book on a digital map or interface.
User Authentication	It provides a secure login for users to access their accounts and search history.
Book Availability Status	Displays the current availability status of books (available, checked out, etc.).
Real-Friendly Updates	Updates book location and availability in real-time.
User-Friendly Interface	Ensures the system is easy to navigate and understand for all users.
Reporting and Analytics	Generates reports on system usage, book searches, and user activity.
Multi-Platform Compatibility	Supports access from various devices (PCs, tablets, smartphones).
System Performance	Ensures the system performs efficiently under load and provides quick responses.
Accessibility Features	Includes features for users with disabilities (e.g., screen readers, high contrast mode).
Security and Data Privacy	Implements measures to protect user data and system integrity.
Customization Options	Allows customization of the search and display settings based on user preferences.

Prototyping. Initial prototypes were developed using a user-centered design approach based on the gathered requirements. PHP, C++, Python, Java, and MySQL were used to develop and create the system's functional models. Prototypes were tested in small user groups, with feedback collected on usability, performance, and overall user satisfaction. Each iteration focused on refining the system's usability and aligning it closely with user expectations.

System Development and Implementation. The development phase involved building the system architecture, as shown in Fig. 2, using RFID and BLE technologies.

Figure 2. Syarwm Architecture.

This phase also includes coding the software and integrating the necessary hardware components, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. HARDWARE COMPONENT REQUIREMENT

Hardware Component	Function
RFID sticker tag	Facilitate item identification, check-in/check-out, and inventory management.
MFRC522 RFID Module Scan RFID	Enables data exchange with microcontroller for access control and inventory management
RFID readers	Detects and reads information from RFID tags for automated tracking.
NodeMCU ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module – Wi-Fi Microcontroller	Provides wireless connectivity and control of IoT applications.
5V Piezo Active Buzzer	Emits audio signals for alerts.
LED – Status Indicator	Provides visual feedback on the system's operational state.

Figure 3 shows the hardware architecture diagram supporting multiple client types, including students, faculty members, and librarians. This browser-based access ensures platform independence, allowing users to interact with the library system regardless of their device type. The system is secured by a network

firewall, which manages and protects communication between the client devices and the library system hosted on the server. The web server handles multiple subsystems at the core of the system. The UIs provide tailored interfaces for the users. The Business Logic Layer processes the requests received from both user interfaces, executing core functionalities. Additionally, the system uses services and dynamic HTML pages to

provide responsive, up-to-date user content based on their interactions. The database server stores the library's data, including book information, user details, and real-time location data. RFID tags and BLE beacons are key technologies in the system that enable the real-time detection and tracking of books within the library.

Figure. 3. Hardware Architecture.

Testing and Refinement. The system was tested in a real- world library setting, simulating typical usage conditions. Testing included both technical performance assessments and user-focused usability testing. Rigorous tests were conducted on system response time, accuracy of proximity detection, and interface intuitiveness. Feedback from users was collected and analyzed to refine the system, ensuring it met both technical and practical requirements.

Usability Assessment

To evaluate the system's effectiveness, a comprehensive usability assessment was conducted

using the Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire (PSSUQ) [9], a recognized tool for measuring user satisfaction with system usability.

1. Testing Environment. Usability testing was conducted in a controlled library setting with RFID readers, BLE beacons, and mobile devices. The environment was designed to replicate actual usage scenarios, ensuring the data collected reflected the system's real-world performance.

2. Participant Selection. A diverse group of participants was selected, including 15 students, five system developers, ten faculty members, and two

librarians. Participants were chosen based on varying levels of technological proficiency and library usage frequency to ensure a broad representation of user feedback.

3. Testing Procedures. Participants were tasked with using the system to perform common library tasks, such as searching for a book by title and locating it via the proximity detection feature. Key metrics such as task completion time, error rates, and user satisfaction scores were recorded.

4. Data Collection and Analysis. Data from the PSSUQ were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean scores and standard deviations for each usability dimension. MS Excel was used for quantitative analysis, while qualitative feedback from follow-up interviews was categorized and analyzed for common themes.

D. Ethical Considerations

Ethical guidelines were strictly followed throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were informed of the study's objectives, procedures, and potential risks. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw at any point without repercussions. All collected data were anonymized to ensure privacy, and digital and physical records were securely stored. Data confidentiality was maintained using encrypted storage solutions to protect participant information.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Current State of Library Resource Management

Traditional library resource management systems face significant challenges locating books and other materials, largely due to their reliance on manual processes such as barcode scanning and physical catalog searches.

These methods are time-consuming and prone to human error, often leading to user frustration when materials are misplaced or incorrectly shelved. Studies have shown that inefficiencies affect user satisfaction and library operations [10]. For example, the researchers found during the initial audit of

CHMSU Library that 65% of books were located on the correct shelves but were not in their designated locations, complicating the search process for users. Furthermore, 5.6% of the books were completely misplaced.

These findings are consistent with previous research, highlighting that libraries lack real-time tracking capabilities [11]. As a result, library staff are often burdened with time-intensive tasks such as conducting physical inventories and handling user complaints about misplaced materials.

This inefficient use of resources underlines the need for modern, automated systems and the integration of technologies such as RFID and BLE beacons. Recent research has demonstrated that these technologies can significantly improve the accuracy of resource tracking, reduce manual labor, and enhance user satisfaction by providing real-time updates on the location of library materials [12].

B. Library Book Finding System

Implementing the Library Book Finding System with Proximity Detection, using RFID and BLE beacon technologies, was designed to significantly improve the efficiency and user experience of locating books within the library. This system integrates hardware and software components to offer a robust real-time book tracking and resource management solution.

User Authentication and Access Control. The system begins with a secure authentication module that verifies users' identities before granting access to the application, ensuring a secure and role-based environment. This module assigns appropriate access levels based on user roles, providing administrative access for librarians while students and faculty receive user-level access. Unique login credentials, such as ID numbers, maintain security, preventing unauthorized access and ensuring data protection, which is critical for library systems [13].

Fig. 4 shows the flowchart of the authentication process and demonstrates how essential this step is for maintaining system integrity and protecting sensitive library data from unauthorized access [14].

Figure. 4. User Authentication Flowchart.

Book Search and Location Display. Once authenticated, users can search for books by title, author, subject, or keywords. The mobile application provides real-time access to the library's database, displaying book locations alongside an interactive map to assist users in navigating the library. This feature is particularly useful in larger libraries, where locating specific books can be challenging. Similar systems integrating book search with location services have been shown to significantly enhance user satisfaction by reducing the time required to find materials [11]. The system also provides additional information, such as the book's availability status, due dates, and loan history, further improving user convenience [2].

Integration of RFID and BLE Technologies. The system achieves real-time book tracking by integrating RFID tags and BLE beacons, providing highly accurate location data. RFID tags affixed to each book emit signals that strategically placed RFID readers detect, while BLE beacons further enhance location precision by supplying proximity-

based information. RFID and BLE technologies have been widely recognized for reliability in library management systems, particularly real-time inventory tracking [3]. The signals captured by beacons are processed and transmitted to a centralized database, ensuring that users have access to real-time, accurate information regarding the availability and position of library resources.

Mobile Application Interface. The mobile application, developed on the Android 8.0 platform, serves as the primary interface for users. The app is powered by a Qualcomm Snapdragon 600 series processor with 4 GB of RAM and ensures smooth performance and efficient multitasking. High-resolution touchscreens allow users to interact with the app easily, view detailed book information, and navigate the library map. The app also supports real-time notifications, such as reminders for due dates and alerts when books are returned or placed on hold. Such mobile interfaces have been shown to improve user engagement and satisfaction in library environments significantly [14]. If a book is on the shelf, the application guides the user to its location using a red line, making the retrieval process more efficient.

System Performance and User Interaction. Essential hardware features, such as Bluetooth for BLE beacon communication, Wi-Fi for real-time data updates, and GPS for precise indoor navigation, enhance the system's performance. These technologies ensure that users can locate books efficiently, manage library accounts (e.g., renewals, holds), and receive real-time updates on book availability. Recent studies have shown that mobile systems with integrated Bluetooth and Wi-Fi functionalities optimize library operations and user interactions [5]. A battery capacity of 3000 mAh or higher supports extended usage, while the high-resolution touchscreen improves user interaction, making the app highly responsive and intuitive.

Real-Time Book Status Features. One of the most notable features of the system is its ability to provide real-time status updates on library materials. Users can quickly determine whether a book is available, borrowed, or reserved. This capability is crucial for managing high-demand resources, as it provides

instant notifications on due dates, overdue items, and reservation status. By offering users immediate access to this information, the system helps prevent the frustration of searching for unavailable books. It encourages more proactive engagement with library resources, enabling users to make better-informed decisions about their borrowing activities. Such features have been shown to improve the efficiency of library management and user satisfaction by allowing patrons to stay engaged and informed about the library's offerings [15].

C. Usability and Functional Assessment.

Table III presents the results of the usability assessment. The criteria assessed include System Usefulness, Information Quality, Interface Quality, and Overall Usability. The mean scores for all criteria range from 4.66 to 4.70, with low standard deviations (SD) indicating a high level of consistency in user responses. All categories received a "Strongly Agree"

interpretation, reflecting overall positive user feedback and satisfaction with the system's usability.

TABLE III. PSSUQ RESULTS

PSSUQ Criteria	Mean	SD	Interpretation
System Usefulness	4.69	0.38	Strongly Agree
Information Quality	4.70	0.36	Strongly Agree
Interface Quality	4.66	0.53	Strongly Agree
Overall Usability	4.69	0.36	Strongly Agree

The system's usefulness is reflected in the end users' ratings, with a mean score of 4.69, which strongly agrees with the system's effectiveness. This high rating suggests that users find the system valuable in improving their ability to locate books and manage library resources. This aligns with the findings of [16], who identified productivity, system quality, and service quality as critical factors in predicting the acceptance of systems like LMS [17]. Similarly, in the context of the library system, these factors play a crucial role in determining user satisfaction and system adoption.

The information quality of the system was also highly rated, with a mean score of 4.70, indicating strong

agreement among users that the information provided by the system is accurate, relevant, and reliable. This result underscores the importance of maintaining high-quality information to meet user expectations and enhance the overall experience. As supported by [18], continuous monitoring, assessment, and enhancement of information quality are essential in intelligent systems. Regular updates and improvements to the mobile application can ensure that users receive up-to-date and precise data, critical for maintaining trust and engagement with the system.

The interface quality received a rating of 4.66, which strongly agrees with the mobile application's usefulness, reliability, and aesthetics. The smooth and intuitive interface design contributes to a positive user experience by making it easy for users to navigate the system and access the information they need efficiently. According to [19], tools specifically designed to perform functional tests and validate user interface elements can significantly improve the reliability and functionality of mobile applications. In this case, the well-designed interface of the library system not only enhances user satisfaction but also ensures the system's overall stability and ease of use.

The overall usability of the system, reflected by a mean score of 4.69, demonstrates that end users strongly agree with the system's overall performance and effectiveness. This positive evaluation indicates that the system meets the users' expectations regarding ease of use, functionality, and overall experience. Similar findings were observed in the usability evaluation of the Sinovi website [12], where user experience was positively rated in terms of attractiveness, efficiency, and dependability. However, continuous enhancements are necessary to address potential issues and improve the user experience. In the case of the library system, the high usability score suggests that the system is performing well. Still, regular feedback from users and iterative improvements will help maintain and elevate this level of performance over time.

IV. CONCLUSION

Integrating RFID and Bluetooth-based proximity detection technologies into library information infrastructures has proven to be highly effective in improving the efficiency of book and material location within library environments. The system developed in this study received overwhelmingly positive feedback, with 85% of users reporting improved efficiency in locating books, 88% affirming the accuracy and reliability of the information provided, and 81% to 83% expressing satisfaction with the user-friendly interface. These findings highlight the significant positive impact of the system on both library operations and user satisfaction.

However, several limitations of the study must be acknowledged. First, although the usability testing sample was diverse, it did not fully represent the entire spectrum of library users, particularly those with varying levels of technological proficiency or differing usage patterns. This limitation may affect the generalizability of the findings to other library settings or broader populations. Additionally, the study was conducted in a controlled environment, which may not accurately reflect real-world conditions where fluctuating network quality, hardware malfunctions, or unexpected user behavior could affect system performance. These limitations are justified as they reflect common constraints in preliminary usability studies, where the focus is often on testing system functionality in a stable environment before broader implementation.

To address these limitations, future research should explore larger-scale implementations of the system across various library types and geographic locations to better assess its effectiveness in different contexts. Long-term evaluations are also necessary to measure the system's sustained impact on library operations, user satisfaction, and overall efficiency. Furthermore, integrating emerging technologies like machine learning and artificial intelligence could enhance the system's capabilities, enabling more personalized and predictive library services. These technologies could help optimize resource management and user experience by anticipating

user needs and adapting to changing library dynamics, offering new avenues for innovation in library management systems.

In conclusion, while this study demonstrates the potential of RFID and Bluetooth-based systems to revolutionize library environments, addressing the identified limitations and expanding research into new technological applications will ensure that such systems remain at the forefront of library service innovation.

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